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Article

Life with Cats: Academic Procrastination and Quality of Life among Undergraduates in Jordan

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of cat guardianship on academic procrastination and quality of life among university students in Jordan. Using an experimental design, data were collected from 47 self-identified academic procrastinators. Participants adopted cats and participated in an open-structured care program over four months. Academic procrastination and quality of life were measured using validated scales at three points: pre-intervention, post-intervention, and a two-month follow-up. Results showed a significant decrease in academic procrastination and notable improvements in quality of life after the intervention. These positive effects were sustained at follow-up, with no significant differences observed between post-test and follow-up scores across quality-of-life dimensions, including mental health, social relationships, and environmental factors. The findings suggest that cat guardianship may be an effective intervention for enhancing student well-being and reducing procrastination. The study also examines cultural significance which may reinforce the intervention's effectiveness by promoting a sense of structured responsibility among students.

Keywords: cat guardianship; pet ownership; academic procrastination; quality of life; university students; Arab culture

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1. Introduction

Procrastination, which has been characterized as a poorly understood human characteristic (Ferrari, 1994), is the tendency to postpone making a decision or performing a task (Ferrari & Tibbett, 2020). In its chronic form, procrastination is estimated to affect 20% of the general population (Diaz-Morales & Ferrari, 2014). The evidence for cultural variation regarding procrastination, however, is meager (Lu et al., 2022). Academic procrastination is a domain-specific behavior in which students postpone the completion of academic tasks (González-Brignardello et al., 2023). Up to 95% of undergraduate students report struggling with academic procrastination (Rad, 2025), which is associated with a wide range of negative consequences, including loss of student well-being and dropout (González-Brignardello et al., 2023). College students face diverse challenges, including academic adjustment, adapting to institutional settings, and navigating relationships with instructors. Procrastination is more than a simple matter of time management; it is a complex problem that encompasses the cognitive, behavioral, and psychological domains (Furlan & Cristofolini, 2022).

Among university students, procrastination has been shown to impact both academic and personal well-being. Putting off tasks that can be done tomorrow has been linked to decreased academic performance, increased stress, and lower life satisfaction (Babu et al., 2019). Students often avoid key academic tasks, such as studying for tests or completing course assignments, despite being aware of the negative consequences of such decisions (Lu et al., 2022). Studies have found that students procrastinate not only when they dislike particular activities but also when they struggle with self-control, self-esteem, and perfectionism (Awwad et al., 2022). Self-efficacy for self-regulation has been linked to academic procrastination. A relationship between procrastination, self-efficacy, and psychological vulnerability among undergraduates has also been observed (Huang et al., 2023). These studies highlight the complex connection between procrastination and psychological traits, which have important implications for students' mental health and overall well-being.

Pet guardianship is a significant global phenomenon (Islam & Towell, 2013). A large and growing body of research has examined the effects of companion animal ownership (also known as “pet ownership” and “pet keeping”) and quality of life (Herzog, 2011). Within this broad literature, which saw significant expansion following the pet adoption phenomenon during COVID-19, cat guardianship (compared to dog guardianship) has remained a relatively understudied subject, perhaps due to the widespread notion that cats are a rather independent species (Currin-McCulloch et al., 2021; Ravenscroft et al., 2021). Nonetheless, studies have found that human-cat interaction correlates positively with several dimensions of quality of life. Interaction with cats has been shown to improve mood, activate areas of the brain responsible for emotion regulation, and produce overall health benefits (Barcelos et al., 2023). Stroking or patting cats has been reported to lower blood pressure and reduce headaches (Ravenscroft et al., 2021). Researchers have also reported that interacting with cats lowers cortisol levels, thus reducing anxiety (Nagasawa et al., 2023). The rhythmic sound of a cat's purr has been shown to have a calming effect on the listener (Currin-McCulloch et al., 2021). However, the jury is still out on the effects of cat guardianship

and human wellbeing, with inconsistent results across studies on pet-keeping and better human health (Islam & Towell, 2013; Herzog, 2011; Scoresby et al., 2021; Applebaum et al., 2020).

Cats have long enjoyed a privileged status in Arab societies. The feline image appears in Islamic cultural traditions, religious beliefs, and everyday life (Campo, 2009). Among Muslims, the appreciation of felines dates back to the time of the Prophet Muhammad, who is said to have had a particular affinity for them (Foltz, 2006). Islamic teachings emphasize kindness to animals, and many hadiths, which are records of the sayings and actions of the Prophet Mohammed (Campo, 2009), encourage the humane treatment of cats, highlighting their spiritual qualities. Unlike dogs, which require, according to some interpretations of Islamic law, ritual purification for contact, cats are considered inherently pure. This perspective has contributed to their widespread acceptance in households, public spaces, and even religious institutions throughout the Arab world (Foltz, 2006).

In Arab cultures, where a high value is placed on hospitality and family ties, cats provide an additional source of emotional support and companionship, particularly for those who live alone. Their presence fosters mindfulness and relaxation, encouraging individuals to appreciate the present moment – an idea that aligns with Islamic teachings on gratitude (Merini, 2024). Furthermore, caring for cats can help individuals manage loneliness, depression, and other emotional challenges. Cats also contribute to social cohesion within Arab communities. In cities across the Middle East and North Africa, street cats are cared for collectively rather than being the responsibility of a single individual. This communal care reflects the cultural emphasis on shared responsibility and compassion. Shopkeepers and residents often leave food and water for local cats, creating a tacit connection among community members (Foltz, 2006; Merini, 2024). Conversations about street cats serve as social icebreakers, fostering friendly interactions and strengthening community ties (Mittermaier, 2025). For families, particularly those with young children, caring for a cat teaches the values of responsibility, empathy, and patience (Mahmoud, 2020). Islamic teachings emphasize kindness to animals as a key virtue, and raising children with pets can reinforce these moral principles from an early age (Masri, 2016). The important benefits of cat guardianship, particularly in the Arab world, are well-established. However, the impact of such guardianship on specific habits, including academic procrastination, remains an open question.

This study aims to investigate the impact of cat guardianship on the quality of life and procrastination levels of undergraduates. First, it aims to examine if there are differences between academic procrastination with cat guardianship. Second, it seeks to examine whether there are differences in the quality of life with cat guardianship.

2. Research Methods

2.1 Study Design

This study employed an experimental research design to investigate the effects of cat guardianship on academic procrastination and quality of life among university students.

2.2 Participants and Recruitment

The study recruited 47 undergraduate students at the University of Jordan, 14 males (29.8%) and 33 females (70.2%). The mean age of participants was 20.21 years, with ages ranging from 19 to 21 years. A paper poster was distributed across various university faculties, and an online announcement was posted on the University of Jordan's official social media platforms (Appendix 3), targeting students who self-identified as academic procrastinators. The poster and announcement aimed to reach the student body effectively by combining physical and digital outreach. The paper posters were placed in high-traffic student areas within the faculties, while the social media announcement leveraged the university's online platforms to engage students directly and encourage their participation.

Participants were informed about the study's requirements, including the responsibility of owning a cat. Among the students who responded, a sample was formed comprising individuals who agreed to participate in the study, as per the Institutional Review Board (IRB) ethics criteria at the University of Jordan. Participants were instructed to adopt cats from local veterinary clinics that support pet adoption. The adoption process included detailed guidance on caring for the cats, such as maintaining their hygiene, providing appropriate food, and engaging in specific daily activities as outlined in the care program provided by the clinics. The study population consisted of self-selected undergraduate students at the University of Jordan in the academic year 2022/2023. The final sample included 47 students (14 males and 33 females), between the ages of 19 and 21. Four participants withdrew during the study, leaving 43 participants in the experimental group. Table 1 below shows the distribution of participants by age and gender.

2.3 Research Tools

2.3.1 Academic Procrastination Scale

The Academic Procrastination Scale was used to assess the level of academic procrastination among participants, as adopted by Al Sirhan and Al-Sawalha (2017). The scale includes 21 items which are answered on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 'does not apply to me at all' to 5 'applies to me to a very large extent' (Appendix 1). It measures procrastination behavior in various domains, including course-related assignments, exam preparation, as well as subsequent daily lesson follow-up. Content validity was ensured by submitting the scale to a cohort of eight academics in the field of psychology and education at the University of Jordan. Out of the total items on the scale, the panel considered whether the items were relevant and appropriate to the study's goals. With interrater reliability, the rate reached 85%. The scale's validity and the measuring procedure's reliability were checked through a pilot test with 30 students who were not participants in the study. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with coefficients reaching 0.82 for writing academic assignments, 0.76 for exam

preparation, 0.81 for daily follow-up of lessons and attendance and 0.88 for the overall scale. These values indicate a high level of internal consistency, supporting the reliability of the scale for the study.

2.3.2 Quality of Life Scale

The World Health Organization (WHO) Quality of Life instrument was adopted, and a 26-item Quality of Life Scale was used to assess the participants' well-being. The scale consists of 26 items answered on a 4-point Likert scale with the endpoints labeled 1 (a very low degree) and 4 (a very high degree) (Appendix 2). The is divided into four areas: physical health, emotional well-being, social contacts, and environmental conditions. In light of content validity, an independent review of the scale was conducted with the assistance of eight experts in psychology and education. The discriminant analysis also revealed that the subject participants reached an 85% consensus on the item relevance; therefore, the scale was deemed applicable to this study. The reliability of the scale was also assessed using a pilot group of 30 students, who were evaluated with Cronbach's alpha to measure internal consistency. The results were as follows: Physical Health, 0.82; Mental Health, 0.77; Social Relations, 0.75; Environmental Factors, 0.80; and the overall Scale, 0.85. These reliability coefficients confirm the scale's robustness for evaluating quality of life within the context of this study.

2.4 Procedure

The study was conducted at the beginning of the second semester of the academic year 2022/2023. The experimental process included Pre-testing, during which the Academic Procrastination Scale and the Quality-of-Life Scale were administered to participants to establish baseline data. In the intervention phase, participants were instructed to care for their adopted cats for four months using an open-structure caring program that drew on the work of Ravenscroft et al. (14). At the end of the four months, the scales were administered again to assess changes in academic procrastination and quality of life. A follow-up evaluation was conducted two months after the conclusion of the intervention and cessation of the cat care program, during which the scales were re-administered to evaluate the sustainability of the observed changes.

The cats participating in the study were obtained from local veterinary clinics and shelters, ensuring their health and well-being. A permanent foster relationship was established as the basis for the program, with students fully aware that they would be taking on long-term, rather than temporary, responsibility for the cats. All participants received clear and comprehensive instructions on cat care, including feeding schedules, permitted food types, and how to use and clean the litter box regularly. Furthermore, demographic data showed that participants lived either with their families or with roommates, meaning that the responsibility for cat care was likely shared with other household members, a factor that may have influenced the study results

2.5 Statistical Analysis

A range of statistical methods were used to analyze the data to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. Initially, descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, and percentages were used to provide a comprehensive description of the characteristics of the study sample. To assess the effect of cat care on academic procrastination and quality of life, a paired-samples t-test was used. This test is suitable for measuring differences between two measurements of the same group of individuals

before and after the intervention. Before applying this test, the assumption of normality was verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test, which is suitable for small sample sizes (less than 50), confirming the validity and statistical accuracy of the results.

3. Results

To analyze the data, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for all conditions. To address the first aim of this study, the means and standard deviations of participants' scores on the academic procrastination scale were computed on the results of the pre- and post-test applications. The distribution of the scores was then compared for statistical differences. As shown in the use of the paired samples t-test. The t-values were calculated as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean Scores, Standard Deviations, and T-Test Results for Academic Procrastination (Pre- and Post-Test Applications)

Dimension	Application	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value	Effect Size (d)
Writing Academic Assignments	Pre-Test	43	4.41	0.31	17.592	< .001	2.68
	Post-Test	43	1.97	0.51			
Exam Preparation	Pre-Test	43	4.50	0.33	15.576	< .001	2.38
	Post-Test	43	2.01	0.59			
Daily Follow-Up of Lessons and Attendance	Pre-Test	43	4.31	0.41	13.693	< .001	2.09
	Post-Test	43	2.16	0.47			
Academic Procrastination Scale (Overall)	Pre-Test	43	4.40	0.31	18.526	< .001	2.83
	Post-Test	43	2.05	0.46			

The results in Table 1 indicate statistically significant differences ($\alpha = .05$) between pre- and post-test scores for all dimensions and the overall academic procrastination scale. Post-test scores were significantly lower than pre-test scores, suggesting that the intervention reduced academic procrastination levels. For example, the overall mean score decreased from 4.40 in the pre-test to 2.05 in the post-test, with the greatest reduction observed in the "Writing Academic Assignments" dimension (mean = 1.97). These findings support the effectiveness of the pet-guardianship-based program in reducing procrastination and highlight the role of responsibility in pet care.

To explore the second aim, means and standard deviations were calculated for participants' scores on the quality-of-life scale in both pre- and post-test applications. A paired-sample t-test was conducted, and the results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Mean Scores, Standard Deviations, and T-Test Results for Quality of Life (Pre- and Post-Test Applications)

Dimension	Application	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value	Effect Size (d)
Physical Health	Pre-Test	43	2.11	0.47	-12.281	< .001	1.87
	Post-Test	43	3.74	0.24			
Mental Health	Pre-Test	43	1.75	0.38	-12.396	< .001	1.89
	Post-Test	43	3.57	0.35			
Social Relations	Pre-Test	43	1.75	0.56	-10.018	< .001	1.53
	Post-Test	43	3.72	0.44			
Environmental Factors	Pre-Test	43	1.90	0.60	-10.599	< .001	1.61
	Post-Test	43	3.69	0.29			
Quality of Life Scale (Overall)	Pre-Test	43	1.92	0.32	-16.504	< .001	2.52
	Post-Test	43	3.65	0.25			

Table 3 shows statistically significant improvements ($\alpha = 0.05$) in all dimensions and the overall quality of life scale. The overall mean increased from 1.92 in the pre-test to 3.65 in the post-test. Among the dimensions, the largest improvement was observed in "Physical Health" (mean = 3.74), followed by "Social Relations" (mean = 3.72) and "Environmental Factors" (mean = 3.69). These findings confirm that the intervention significantly enhanced participants' quality of life, consistent with previous studies (Ravenscroft et al., 2021), which demonstrated the positive impact of pet guardianship on guardian well-being.

To explore the differences in the mean scores of academic procrastination between post-test and follow-up measurements, t-tests (paired samples) were conducted. Table 3 shows the results. The results show no statistically significant differences at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level between the post-test and follow-up scores on the academic procrastination scale. The overall procrastination mean increased slightly from 2.05 (post-test) to 2.35 (follow-up), $t(19) = -1.954$, $p = .066$. Likewise, the mean scores for the dimension showed no significant differences.

Table 3. Paired-Samples T-Test Results for Academic Procrastination Scores (Post-Test and Follow-Up)

Dimension	Test	N	M	SD	t	P	Effect Size (d)
Writing Academic Assignments	Post-Test	43	1.97	0.51	-1.649	.116	0.25
	Follow-Up	43	2.21	0.45			
Exam Preparation	Post-Test	43	2.01	0.59	-1.798	.088	0.27
	Follow-Up	43	2.36	0.59			
Daily Follow-Up of Lessons and Attendance	Post-Test	43	2.16	0.47	-1.758	.095	0.27
	Follow-Up	43	2.48	0.6			
Academic Procrastination (Overall)	Post-Test	43	2.05	0.46	-1.954	.066	0.30
	Follow-Up	43	2.35	0.43			

Finally, paired-samples t-tests were conducted to compare the average quality of life scores between the post-test and follow-up measurements. Table 4 shows no statistically significant differences between the post-test and follow-up scores on the quality of life scale or its dimensions. The overall quality of life decreased slightly from 3.65 (post-test) to 3.60 (follow-up), $t(19) = 1.389$, $p = .181$. Likewise, the mean scores for the dimension showed no significant differences.

Table 4. Paired-Samples t-test Results for Quality of Life Scores (Post-Test and Follow-Up)

Dimension	Test	N	M	SD	t	p-value	Effect Size (d)																																												
Physical Health	Post-Test	43	3.74	0.24	0.653	.522	0.10																																												
	Follow-Up	43	3.69	0.22				Mental Health	Post-Test	43	3.57	0.35	1.502	.15	0.23	Follow-Up	43	3.48	0.39	Social Relations	Post-Test	43	3.72	0.44	1.377	.185	0.21	Follow-Up	43	3.6	0.4	Environmental Factors	Post-Test	43	3.69	0.29	0.478	.638	0.07	Follow-Up	43	3.66	0.29	Quality of Life Scale (Overall)	Post-Test	43	3.65	0.25	1.389	.181	0.21
Mental Health	Post-Test	43	3.57	0.35	1.502	.15	0.23																																												
	Follow-Up	43	3.48	0.39				Social Relations	Post-Test	43	3.72	0.44	1.377	.185	0.21	Follow-Up	43	3.6	0.4	Environmental Factors	Post-Test	43	3.69	0.29	0.478	.638	0.07	Follow-Up	43	3.66	0.29	Quality of Life Scale (Overall)	Post-Test	43	3.65	0.25	1.389	.181	0.21	Follow-Up	43	3.6	0.21								
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	Follow-Up	43	3.6	0.21																																															

4. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the impact of cat guardianship on academic procrastination and quality of life among university students in Jordan. By leveraging the structured routines and emotional benefits associated with pet care, the intervention sought to foster both behavioural and emotional improvements. The results revealed a significant reduction in procrastination levels and substantial improvements in various dimensions of quality of life, findings that were sustained during the follow-up period.

The positive effects observed can be attributed to the interplay between responsibility and emotional connection. Proper pet care requires adherence to time-sensitive tasks, fostering a sense of accountability, and developing effective time management skills. This accords with existing studies suggesting that responsibility and routine reduce procrastination (Magalhães et al., 2021). Additionally, the emotional bond formed between study participants and their companion cats may have reduced stress and promoted mental well-being, which are critical factors in addressing procrastination (Sirois, 2023). Activities such as stroking and playing with cats may have further alleviated stress by lowering cortisol levels, as reported in previous research

(Ravenscroft et al., 2021). The bonding that occurred between participants and their cats relates to studies suggesting that trust and bonding are key concepts for exploring human-animal interaction (Prato-Previde et al., 2022).

The study's findings also highlight improvements in social relations, mental health, and environmental satisfaction, suggesting that the intervention's benefits extend beyond academic performance. The literature on pet guardianship emphasizes that mental health is a multifaceted concept (Scoresby et al., 2021). Human-cat interaction may foster empathy, reduce loneliness, and enhance communication skills, contributing to overall social well-being. Our findings accord with studies that report higher life satisfaction among pet guardians (Barcelos et al., 2023).

The improved environmental quality reported by participants may reflect the emotional comfort associated with having a pet in one's home. Studies have linked procrastination and short-term mood repair and suggested that the adaptive regulation of emotions can be enhanced by a range of self-regulation strategies (Yang, 2021). Our study suggests that implementing related strategies may reduce the need for procrastination as a mood repair tactic (Yang, 2021).

The integration of cat guardianship within Arab Muslim culture suggests that study participants may have experienced benefits not only from the companionship of the cats but also from the alignment of pet care with religious and cultural values. Islam promotes mindfulness, patience, and compassion – qualities that can be nurtured through the responsibility of caring for a pet. In this context, the act of caring for a cat could serve as an extension of religious and cultural principles, reinforcing positive behaviours such as responsibility and time management.

Beyond religious significance, cats serve as a source of emotional support and social interaction in Arab societies. In cultures where strong family ties and communal living are highly valued, pet guardianship provides an additional level of companionship, particularly for individuals living alone or far from their support systems. Studies have found that such buffering can blunt blood pressure responses to mental stress (Harvie et al., 2025). In the educational setting, the presence of a companion animal has been shown to reduce anxiety levels (Dudley & Knight, 2023) and relieve homesickness (Khalid et al., 2021).

The care responsibilities associated with pet guardianship can help students develop better time management skills, a key factor in reducing procrastination. In Arab Muslim societies, where discipline and structure are emphasized within educational and family settings, the addition of feline care as a structured routine may have reinforced these values. Study participants reported that caring for their cats provided a structured break from academic work, thereby reducing avoidance behaviours commonly associated with procrastination. These results align with research on human-cat interaction and the improvement of executive function, including working memory and problem-solving (Nagasawa et al., 2020).

Furthermore, stress reduction linked to pet interaction aligns with the Islamic concept of maintaining mental well-being. The "pet effect" – namely, the notion that companion animal guardianship can be beneficial to human health and wellbeing – is well-established in the public mind and supported by studies (Harvie et al., 2025; Surma et al., 2022). Our study, which included specific activities associated with cat guardianship, aligns with research that advocates for more operationally defined frameworks to investigate the benefits of human-cat interaction on human well-being (Ravenscroft et al., 2021). These benefits complement Islamic teachings that encourage emotional balance, further reinforcing the idea that pet guardianship can serve as a natural stress-relief mechanism.

4.1 Limitations

This study has several limitations. The generalizability of the findings is limited by the study's small sample size ($n = 47$), the use of a convenience sample, and the absence of a control group. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported measures, which may introduce biases such as social desirability or inaccuracies in self-assessment. This study also did not collect data regarding prior pet ownership and whether participants retained their cats long-term. Future research should address these limitations by employing larger, more diverse samples, using "non-cat-guardian" control/comparison groups, and incorporating objective measures of procrastination and quality of life. Future studies could also benefit from conducting test-retest reliability to strengthen results.

4.2 Implications

First, the findings highlight the therapeutic potential of cat guardianship as a non-traditional intervention for mitigating academic procrastination and enhancing overall well-being among university students. This suggests that institutions of higher education, particularly in Arab societies where cats hold cultural and religious significance, might benefit from implementing pet-friendly initiatives or integrating structured animal-assisted therapy programs into student support services. Such programs could serve as low-cost, culturally resonant interventions to address psychological and behavioural challenges in academic settings. Second, the sustained improvements observed during the follow-up period indicate that cat guardianship may promote long-lasting behavioural and emotional changes. These results suggest that pet guardianship has the potential not only as a temporary support mechanism but also as a foundation for fostering responsibility, emotional regulation, and improved mental health over time. As such, these findings can inform the development of long-term strategies and policies aimed at reducing academic procrastination and improving student outcomes, particularly within culturally sensitive frameworks.

5. Conclusions

This study contributes to the relatively sparse research on the psychological and behavioural effects of cat guardianship. It extends the inquiry on the benefits of living with cats to the specific behaviour of academic procrastination – a global phenomenon with significant physical and mental health burdens. Additionally, it answers the call to broaden the scope of research on procrastination to non-Western populations. While further research is needed to validate and generalize the study's findings, the results suggest the value of incorporating cats into interventions aimed at improving academic procrastination and student well-being.

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Appendix A: Academic Procrastination Scale

This scale consists of a set of statements that describe how you deal with academic tasks that must be accomplished. Please read each statement carefully and indicate the degree to which it applies to you.

Rating Scale:

Very Low – Low – Moderate – High – Very High

1. I regularly complete my assignments day by day; therefore, I do not fall behind in my coursework. *
2. When the exam date approaches, I often find myself distracted by other matters.
3. I usually hurry to complete academic tasks before their deadlines. *
4. I often tell myself that I will do my assignments tomorrow.
5. I usually begin working on academic tasks immediately after they are assigned. *
6. I finish my academic assignments before the deadline. *
7. I delay starting my assignments until the very last moments.
8. I try to find excuses for myself that justify not completing the required academic assignments.
9. I waste a great deal of time.
10. I always finish my important academic assignments with extra time to spare. *
11. I tell myself that I will complete my tasks but then I back out of it.
12. I adhere to the plan I set for myself in order to complete my assignments. *
13. When I encounter difficult tasks, I believe they should be postponed.
14. I delay completing my assignments without justification, even when they are important.
15. I postpone academic tasks regardless of whether they are enjoyable or not.
16. I feel uncomfortable just thinking about having to start my assignments.
17. I do not delay work that I believe must be completed. *
18. I engage in so many recreational activities that I do not have enough time left for studying.
19. I always think that I will have enough time later, so there is no real need to start studying now.
20. Postponing academic tasks is a real problem that I continuously struggle with.
21. I stop studying early in order to do more enjoyable things.

Appendix B: Quality of Life Scale

Rating Scale:

Always – Often – Sometimes – Rarely

1. How would you evaluate your overall quality of life?
2. How satisfied are you with your health?
3. To what extent does your health condition prevent you from doing what you need to do?
4. To what extent do you require medical treatment to carry out your daily activities?
5. To what extent do you enjoy your life?
6. To what extent do you feel that your life has meaning?
7. What is your ability to concentrate?
8. To what extent do you feel safe in your daily life?
9. To what extent is your physical environment healthy?
10. Do you have enough energy to carry out your daily tasks?
11. Do you have the ability to accept your physical appearance?
12. Do you have enough money to meet your needs?

13. Do you have access to the information you need in daily life?
14. To what extent do you have opportunities for leisure activities?
15. What is your ability to move around?
16. How satisfied are you with your sleep?
17. How satisfied are you with yourself?
18. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?
19. How satisfied are you with your sexual life?
20. How satisfied are you with the support you receive from your friends?
21. How satisfied are you with your living conditions (place of residence)?
22. How satisfied are you with the health services provided to you?
23. How satisfied are you with the transportation available to you?
24. In the past few days, have you experienced negative feelings such as bad mood, anxiety, hopelessness, or depression?
25. How satisfied are you with your ability to work?
26. How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily activities?

Appendix C: The text of the announcement which was posted for students at the university

For those who wish to overcome procrastination

(We are conducting a study on the effect of a cat-raising program on academic procrastination)

If you are interested in participating, please contact us at:

Phone: 0777993463

Email: Firas4400@yahoo.com

References

- Al Sirhan, M. T., & Sawalha, M. A. (2017). Academic Procrastination and its Relationship to Self- Regulated Learning among Al- Baiyt University Students. *Journal of Al-Quds Open University for Educational and Psychological Research and Studies*, 5(17). https://digitalcommons.aaru.edu.jo/jaqou_edpsych/vol5/iss17/11/
- Applebaum, J. W., Tomlinson, C. A., Matijczak, A., McDonald, S. E., & Zsembik, B. A. (2020). The Concerns, Difficulties, and Stressors of Caring for Pets during COVID-19: Results from a Large Survey of U.S. Pet Owners. *Animals*, 10(10), 1882. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101882>
- Awwad, A., Alkhubata, M., Alnajjar, K., Alkhalwaldeh, S., & Alkhalwaldeh, A. (2022). Procrastination in daily academic tasks and its relationship to self-esteem among university students. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6283–6293. <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6ns6.10981>
- Babu, P., Chandra, K., Vanishree, M., & Amritha, N. (2019). Relationship between academic procrastination and self-esteem among dental students in Bengaluru City. *Journal of Indian Association of Public Health Dentistry*, 17(2), 146. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jiaphd.jiaphd.182.18>
- Barcelos, A. M., Kargas, N., Maltby, J., & Mills, D. S. (2023). Potential Psychosocial Explanations for the Impact of Pet Ownership on Human Well-Being: Evaluating and expanding current hypotheses. *Human-Animal Interactions*. <https://doi.org/10.1079/hai.2023.0008>
- Campo, J. E. (2009). *Encyclopedia of Islam*. Infobase Publishing.

- Currin-McCulloch, J., Bussolari, C., Packman, W., Kogan, L., & Erdman, P. (2021). Grounded by Purrs and Petting: Experiences with Companion Cats during COVID-19. *Human-animal Interaction Bulletin*. <https://doi.org/10.1079/hai.2021.0009>
- Díaz-Morales, J. F., & Ferrari, J. R. (2014). More Time to Procrastinators: The Role of Time Perspective. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 305–321). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-07368-2_20
- Dudley, C., & Knight, D. (2023). Impact of therapy dogs on student achievement in rural math classrooms. *Alabama Journal of Educational Leadership*, 10, 59–86. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=source%3A%22Alabama+Journal+of+Educational+Leadership%22&ff1=locTexas&id=EJ1401588>
- Ferrari, J. R. (1994). Dysfunctional procrastination and its relationship with self-esteem, interpersonal dependency, and self-defeating behaviors. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 17(5), 673–679. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(94\)90140-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(94)90140-6)
- Ferrari, J. R., & Tibbett, T. P. (2020). Procrastination. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 4046–4053). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24612-3_2272
- Foltz, R. C. (2006). *Animals in Islamic tradition and Muslim cultures*. Oneworld Publications.
- Furlan, L. A., & Cristofolini, T. (2022). Interventions to Reduce Academic Procrastination: A review of their theoretical bases and characteristics. *Springer eBooks*, 127–147. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-12737-3_9
- González-Brignardello, M. P., Paniagua, A. S., & López-González, M. Á. (2023). Academic Procrastination in Children and Adolescents: A scoping review. *Children*, 10(6), 1016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10061016>
- Harvie, H. M. K., Rodrigo, A., & Giuliano, R. J. (2025). Assessing whether household pets buffer responses to a remote stress induction. *Anthrozoös*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927936.2025.2482328>
- Herzog, H. (2011). The impact of pets on Human Health and Psychological Well-Being. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 20(4), 236–239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721411415220>
- Huang, H., Ding, Y., Liang, Y., Wan, X., Peng, Q., Zhang, Y., Kong, D., & Chen, C. (2023). The association between perfectionism and academic procrastination among undergraduate nursing students: The role of self-efficacy and resilience. *Nursing Open*, 10(10), 6758–6768. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.1922>
- Islam, A., & Towell, T. (2013). Cat and Dog Companionship and well-being: A systematic review. *International Journal of Applied Psychology*, 3(6). <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijap.20130306.01>
- Khalid, A., Rogers, A., Vicary, E., & Brooks, H. (2021). Human- animal interaction to support well- being at university: Experiences of undergraduate students in the UK. *People and Animals the International Journal of Research and Practice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.62845/qemql2i>
- Lu, D., He, Y., & Tan, Y. (2022). Gender, socioeconomic status, cultural differences, education, family size and Procrastination: A Sociodemographic Meta-Analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.719425>
- Magalhães, P., Pereira, B., Oliveira, A., Santos, D., Núñez, J. C., & Rosário, P. (2021). The Mediator Role of Routines on the Relationship between General Procrastination, Academic Procrastination and Perceived Importance of Sleep and Bedtime Procrastination. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(15), 7796. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18157796>

- Mahmoud, F. E. Z. S. (2020). Raising pets at home and the ethical scientific effects on children's behavior. *Sohag University International Journal of Educational Research (SUIJER) /Sohag University International Journal of Educational Research (SUIJER)*, 3(3), 77–92. <https://doi.org/10.21608/suijer.2021.122464>
- Masri, A. B. A. (2016). *Animal welfare in Islam*. Kube Publishing Ltd.
- Merini, M. E. (2024, December 25). *The significance of cats in Arab culture - Arab America*. Arab America. <https://www.arabamerica.com/the-significance-of-cats-in-arab-culture/>
- Mittermaier, A. (2025). CARING FOR CATS IN CAIRO: Urban Grammars of Compassion. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.13340>
- Nagasawa, T., Kimura, Y., Masuda, K., & Uchiyama, H. (2023). Effects of Interactions with Cats in Domestic Environment on the Psychological and Physiological State of Their Owners: Associations among Cortisol, Oxytocin, Heart Rate Variability, and Emotions. *Animals*, 13(13), 2116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13132116>
- Nagasawa, T., Ohta, M., & Uchiyama, H. (2020). Effects of the characteristic temperament of cats on the emotions and hemodynamic responses of humans. *PLoS ONE*, 15(6), e0235188. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235188>
- Prato-Previde, E., Ricci, E. B., & Colombo, E. S. (2022). The complexity of the Human–Animal bond: empathy, attachment and anthropomorphism in Human–Animal relationships and animal hoarding. *Animals*, 12(20), 2835. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12202835>
- Rad, H. F., Bordbar, S., Bahmaei, J., Vejdani, M., & Yusefi, A. R. (2025). Predicting academic procrastination of students based on academic self-efficacy and emotional regulation difficulties. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-87664-7>
- Ravenscroft, S. J., Barcelos, A. M., & Mills, D. S. (2021). Cat-human related activities associated with human well-being. *Human-animal Interaction Bulletin*. <https://doi.org/10.1079/hai.2021.0006>
- Scoresby, K. J., Strand, E. B., Ng, Z., Brown, K. C., Stilz, C. R., Strobel, K., Barroso, C. S., & Souza, M. (2021). Pet Ownership and Quality of Life: A Systematic Review of the literature. *Veterinary Sciences*, 8(12), 332. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vetsci8120332>
- Sirois, F. M. (2023). Procrastination and Stress: A conceptual review of why context matters. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 5031. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20065031>
- Surma, S., Oparil, S., & Narkiewicz, K. (2022). Pet ownership and the risk of arterial hypertension and cardiovascular disease. *Current Hypertension Reports*, 24(8), 295–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-022-01191-8>
- Yang, S. (2021). *The Relationship Between Procrastination and Emotions* [PhD dissertation, University of Sheffield]. https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/30350/1/The%20Relationship%20Between%20Procrastination%20and%20Emotions_ethesis_SY.pdf

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